

Strength adhesion of chorioretinal tissues after the influence of high-frequency microsurgical electric welding with suprachoroid accesses.

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Purpose: To evaluate the strength adhesion of chorioretinal tissues, after the influence of high-frequency microsurgical electric welding, with suprachoroid accesses in order to accelerate the adhesion of tissues in retinal detachment.

Methods: The study was performed on 52 rabbits (104 eyes), which were divided into 4 groups: 10-12 Volt, 12-14(V), 14-16 (V), and a control group. Fragment of the eye wall tissue containing the retinopexy was isolated into five separate groups: 1 hour, 1 week, 2 weeks, and 1 month. The fragment was fixed to the weighing platform of an analytic electronic scale, so that the place of the welding of suprachoroid was in the center of the fragment. A nylon suture (10-0) passed through the retina was elevated by a biomechanical force elongation tester. The reduction in weight at the time of retinopexy rupture was registered as a measure for retinopexy adhesion strength.

Results: After the use of local suprachoroidal high-frequency electric welding with a frequency of 66 kHz using three voltage modes, the strength of chorioretinal adhesion was significantly higher compared with chorioretinal adhesion on the intact retina (control group). In the early post-exposure period (up to 2 weeks), when using the 10-12 V, the strength of the chorioretinal junctions was higher compared to the other higher voltage parameters (12-14 V, 14-16 V). A month after the suprachoroid electric welding was conducted, no significant difference was indicated between the groups.

Conclusion: HFECW with suprachoroidal accesses allows immediately strong chorioretinal adhesion, and could reduce the complications of vitreoretinal surgery.